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Technology Utilization and Project Success: An Empirical Investigation of Project Management Practices Across IT and Non-IT Organizations

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Abstract.

The increasing availability of digital project management tools has transformed how organizations plan, execute, and monitor projects; however, empirical evidence suggests that effective utilization remains inconsistent. This study empirically examines the relationship between technology usage and perceived project performance across IT and non-IT organizations. Primary data were collected through structured questionnaires and interviews with 100 project stakeholders, including project managers, team leads, engineers, sponsors, and end users. Descriptive and statistical analyses were employed to evaluate technology adoption patterns, communication effectiveness, planning and control practices, and execution efficiency. The results indicate that although respondents strongly acknowledge the importance of technology for project communication, coordination, and monitoring, advanced project management tools are significantly underutilized. Basic applications such as email systems and standalone scheduling software dominate usage, while integrated project management information systems and cloud-based platforms show limited adoption. Notably, approximately 70% of respondents reported only average or below-average project success, highlighting a gap between technological availability and realized performance outcomes. The findings suggest that technology contributes positively to project execution only when supported by leadership commitment, organizational readiness, and user capability. The study offers practical implications for improving digital maturity and project success through structured, top-down technology integration strategies.

Keywords: Project Management Technology, Project Performance, Technology Adoption, Project Management Information Systems (PMIS), Digital Transformation, IT and Non-IT Organizations, Empirical Study